

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D1.6: Minutes of 3rd Advisory Board meeting

WP1 – Project Management

This project has received funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation
programme under grant agreement No 649493

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	649493	Acronym	STEP	
Full Project Title	Societal and political engagement of young people in environmental issues			
Start Date	1 st June 2015	Duration	30 months	
Project URL	www.step4youth.eu			
Deliverable	D 1.5 - Minutes of 2 nd Advisory Board meetings			
Work Package	WP 1 - Project Management			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	1 April 2017	Actual	29 March 2017
Nature	R - Report	Dissemination Level	P – Public	
Lead Beneficiary	1 - DRAXIS			
Responsible Author	Ms. Panagiota Syropoulou Ms. Maria Vogiatzi Mr. Christodoulos Keratidis			
Contributions from	Mr. Josué Alonso			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1.0	27/03/2017	Draft		Mr. Christodoulos Keratidis, Ms. Panagiota Syropoulou, Ms. Maria Vogiatzi
2.0	28/03/2017	Draft	Internal review	Mr. Josué Alonso
3.0	29/03/2017	Final		Ms. Panagiota Syropoulou

Disclaimer

The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© STEP Consortium, 2015

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

- 1 Executive summary 4
- 2 Introduction 4
- 3 Update of the EEAB list 4
- 4 EEAB activities..... 5
- 5 Feedback and actions..... 6
- 6 Conclusions 9
- ANNEX A - Members of the EEAB..... 9
- ANNEX B – STEP EEAB update (November 2016)..... 10

1 Executive summary

The current deliverable is the third report on the activities of the STEP project's External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB). The members of the EEAB were contacted either through physical meetings or via Internet using WebEx. This deliverable summarizes the recommendations that these experts have provided to the project consortium from M15 (August 2016) until M22 (March 2017). During the previous months of the project's implementation, several activities with the members of the EEAB have been organized and the feedback gained was reported in the deliverables D1.2 and D1.5.

Regarding the structure of the current document, in Chapter 2 a short introduction on the EEAB role within the STEP project is provided, while in Chapter 3 any changes made on the board from M15 until M22 are presented. The meetings held during this period between EEAB members and STEP partners are presented in Chapter 4, and, finally, some of the most important recommendations of the experts to the STEP partners are summarized in Chapter 5 accompanied with the actions taken by the consortium to address these points.

2 Introduction

Besides the communication between the STEP partners, it is very important to convey ideas, research and outcomes of the project to relevant stakeholders, to receive their feedback, and make sure that the final outcomes of the project are aligned with the vision potential users. In order to achieve that, an External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) has been established early in the project (M3) to review the project activities and outcomes, identify the strong and weak points with respect to the objectives of the project, and provide recommendations during all the project's phases.

The STEP EEAB consists of a group of excellent professionals in diverse relevant fields as well as members of potential user groups. The STEP partners are regularly providing the EEAB with the appropriate project information and update of the project' progress. ANNEX B – STEP EEAB update (November 2016) shows an example of the regular report which is sent to the EEAB members to facilitate the exchange of information about the status of the project.

3 Update of the EEAB list

The EEAB list may be updated throughout the duration of the project in case a new need for consultation will emerge. In addition, as the STEP EEAB members are people who are engaged with various activities in their fields of expertise, they may change position during the project.

For the given period (August 2016-March 2017), the following changes were made on the Board:

Eva Theisz has changed position

Eva Theisz was Director of Support and Cooperation at the Swedish Agency for Youth and Civil Society, a government agency that aims to ensure that young people have access to influence and welfare and support the government in issues relevant to civil society policy. Now she is Deputy Director of International Affairs at the Swedish public employment service. Capitalizing the experience she gained through her previous activities, Eva will continue to offer her consultation services to STEP as a member of its

EEAB.

Babis Tsitlakidis has changed position

Babis Tsitlakidis was Chief Digital Officer of the Municipality of Thessaloniki, being in charge of the eGovernment and Digital Transformation procedures in the operational planning of the Municipality. Babis is now working at DG CONNECT, Unit of eHealth and ICT for Wellbeing and Ageing, focusing on policy regarding interoperability matters. He is still a Seconded National Expert of the Municipality of Thessaloniki, Greece. Babis continues to be interested on the STEP project, thus he reserves his position as a member of the STEP EEAB.

Lorenzo Floresta joined the STEP EEAB

Lorenzo Floresta is the coordinator of the International Youth Panel of the Horizon 2020 project “CATCH-EyoU - Constructing active citizenship with European youth: Policies, Practices, Challenges and Solutions” (www.catcheyou.eu). He was asked to join the STEP EEAB as his expertise and experience on the topic of youth participation will be useful for STEP. With a master’s degree in Law and International Master in European Studies and Policy Advisor, Lorenzo has been the President of *Giovani Senza Frontiere* (GIOSEF) since 2010. Until 2015 he was board member of the Italian National Youth Council, where he also held the position of Vice President of the Foreign Commission. He was board member for the Sicilian Regional Institute for the Student rights, and of the Italian National Forum of the Civil Service.

The full list of the EEAB members can be found in ANNEX A - Members of the EEAB, while short CVs of all members are also provided in the [STEP website](#).

4 EEAB activities

During these 22 months of the STEP project, the consortium has kept a continuous and fluent communication with the members of the EEAB. All the contacted members gave valuable feedback which was reported in the deliverables D1.2 and D1.5.

For the given period (August 2016-March 2017), the following activities took place so that the consortium could acquire feedback from the EEAB members:

- *Kerstin Franzl*, as expert on public participation and having strong experience on youth participation through the project EUth, reviewed the STEP deliverable D5.1-“Definition of STEP pilots and evaluation methodology” in October 2016.
- Panagiota Syropoulou (DRAXIS) had a meeting with *Epaminondas Christofilopoulos*, Greek National Contact Point for Horizon 2020 for Environment, Energy and Transport, on the 14th of November 2016 at the premises of DRAXIS. The purpose of the meeting was to demonstrate live the STEP e-participation platform and the social media monitoring tool to Epaminondas so that we receive his feedback and thoughts.
- Maria Vogiatzi, Panagiota Syropoulou (DRAXIS) and Roxana Nica (YEE) had a conference call with *Christiane Klemm* on the 20th of February 2017. Christiane is representative of the German ecological youth organization [FÖJ Aktiv e.V.](#), while in December 2016 she was a member of the official Youth Delegation at the COP13 of the Convention on Biodiversity in Mexico. The purpose of the call was to explore the viewpoint of a potential user about the

STEP platform and to discuss new ways of user engagement through EU youth organizations' streams.

- Maria Vogiatzi and Panagiota Syropoulou (DRAXIS) had another meeting with *Epaminondas Christofilopoulos* (21 February 2017) to present him the new platform's features and investigate synergies between the STEP project and Phemonoe Lab (www.phemonoe.eu), in which Epaminondas is Chief Executive Officer.
- Maria Vogiatzi and Christodoulos Keratidis (DRAXIS) had a meeting with *Lorenzo Floresta* during the [CATCH-EyoU Conference](#) that took place on 2-4 of March 2017. The purpose of the meeting was to explore ways of common dissemination of the two projects, as well as potential synergies with relevant youth organizations and other NGO's.

The feedback that was acquired from the EEAB members during the above activities are presented in the following Chapter.

5 Feedback and actions

This Chapter focuses on the most important remarks pointed out during the activities described in Chapter 4.

1) Kerstin pointed out that the evaluation process of the STEP pilots should be distinguished between continuous bug reporting and acquisition of users' feedback on the platform's usability. For the latter she suggested that the STEP partners should include (in the evaluation planning) slots for transferring the feedback results to the software developers. According to Kerstin's experience within the EUth project, this is a time-consuming procedure, so the STEP partners should save resources for this.

<These remarks have already been taken into account and deliverable D5.1: "Definition of STEP pilots and evaluation methodology" has been revised accordingly.>

2) Based on his experience, Epaminondas believes that the top-down approach of STEP may not have broad acceptance, as public authorities are usually reluctant to change their decision-making procedures. On the other hand, Epaminondas pointed that the bottom-up approach of STEP has many potential uses as, in this concept, STEP could be used for specific campaigns initiated by communities of citizens.

<The pilot partners of STEP are the proof that there are a lot of public authorities that need a tool like STEP and are willing to open their decision-making procedures. These authorities act as a test bed for the identification of user's acceptance. In addition, the project consortium has come in contact with external public authorities that are interested to adopt STEP in their procedures. A remarkable example is the one of the Municipality of Thessaloniki that will voluntary use STEP. Regarding the bottom-up approach of STEP, various citizens' communities have expressed their interest to initiate petitions through the STEP platform.>

3) Epaminondas recommended that the Municipality of Jun in Granada could be a case study for STEP, as this specific Municipality performs the majority of their internal procedures through twitter and also their citizens use twitter to contact the Municipality (<https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2015/jul/02/twitter-jun-spain-bureaucracy-local-government>).

<The STEP partners has already contacted the Municipality of Jun to explore potential synergies.>

4) Christiane generally liked the STEP platform and its graphical identity, from a user's perspective. She pointed that STEP could be very useful for organisations like the one in which she is member. However, the platform should be fully functional and tested before its official launch, otherwise the users will be disappointed and quit using it. A minor remark in the registration process is that it should be prominent that the addition of a profile photo is optional, otherwise some users may be discouraged from signing in. Christiane is also interested to use the STEP timeline feature for her organization in order to acquire the opinion of its members on local environmental issues.

<The consortium will take into account all the above remarks and will make any additional changes to the platform if necessary. The abovementioned environmental organization will be invited to participate in STEP dialogues using the timeline feature.>

5) In our second meeting with Epaminondas, he suggested that a tool like STEP should be accompanied by online and offline activities so that it attracts a significant number of users. An idea is that public authorities add a widget on their official website or on their Facebook account.

<This remark has already been taken into account in the design of the STEP local dissemination plans. Online and offline dissemination activities are constantly organized throughout the whole duration of the project, while info kiosks are placed outside the venue of the launch events for those with no internet access.>

6) According to Epaminondas, the registration procedure may be a repellent for some potential users as only if they are personally interested in a specific topic they will be willing to enter their personal information.

<This suggestion has been taken into account, thus in the current version of the platform registration is optional and someone can enter their post by entering only their name and email.>

7) Epaminondas expressed his interest to use the timeline feature of the STEP platform for the purposes of the Phemonoe Lab to ask for the public's opinion on crucial environmental topics, e.g. eco-business.

<DRAXIS will involve the Phemonoe Lab to the STEP timeline feature.>

8) A meeting was held between Lorenzo Floresta and the members of the STEP team (Christodoulos Keratidis and Maria Vogiatzi) during the Catch-EyoU Conference that took place on 2-4 March in Athens. At the meeting the STEP team presented in detail the STEP project and the platform and an extensive discussion on STEP's dissemination strategy followed. Christodoulos expressed STEP's consortium interest in creating synergies with youth organizations and other NGO's that could possibly use the STEP solution, as well as disseminate the project within their network. Lorenzo introduced Christodoulos and Maria to: Eva Majewski, Secretary General of the Young Caucus of CDU/CSU in the German Bundestag and active in a various other youth associations; Kuldar Adel, representative of the Estonian National Youth Council; Domniki Kouitzoglou, ex-Vice President of the Hellenic National Youth Council and active in the organization of youth events. All three representatives were interested in the STEP project and in becoming members of the STEP Network of Interest. Domniki, who is also a member of the Greek Scout Association, suggested to disseminate STEP within the Association and to explore possible ways of using STEP.

<The STEP consortium will use all the dissemination streams that were suggested by Lorenzo to effectively involve more users to the STEP activities. The abovementioned associations will be constantly informed on the project's progress, while they will also be invited to participate in STEP dialogues using the timeline feature.>

Table 1: Indicative feedback and STEP actions

Name	Recommendations/ remarks	STEP WP
Kerstin Franzl	In the evaluation planning, STEP should include slots for transferring the user feedback results to the software developers. STEP should also take into account that this is a time-consuming procedure.	WP5
Epaminondas Christofilopoulos	STEP should take into consideration the possible reluctance of the public authorities to use the STEP platform.	WP5
Christiane Klemm	The STEP platform should be fully functional and tested before its official launch.	WP3, WP5
Epaminondas Christofilopoulos	The STEP platform should accompanied by online and offline activities so that to attract more users.	WP5, WP7
Epaminondas Christofilopoulos	The registration to the STEP platform should be optional so that it will not act as a repellent for potential users.	WP3, WP5

6 Conclusions

The STEP consortium is in close collaboration with the External Experts Advisory Board (EEAB) members who are individually contacted whenever a consultation for the project's progress is needed. The current document presents the activities that were organized with the STEP EEAB from August 2016 until March 2017, the feedback acquired from the experts, and the actions that the STEP consortium took (or plan to take) to address these recommendations. Until the end of the project (November 2017), the STEP EEAB members will continue to be updated on the project's progress, while individual meetings will be held with them and, if necessary, some of them will be invited in the project's meetings. All these actions will be reported on the final Advisory Board report (D1.7) in November 2017.

ANNEX A - Members of the EEAB

Name	Location	Position	Personal website
Ms. Kerstin Franzl	Berlin, Germany	Coordinator of the project EUth	http://goo.gl/LuTtRe
Dr. Catriona Macaulay	Edinburgh, UK	Head of User Research and Engagement at The Scottish Government	https://www.linkedin.com/in/catmacaulay
Dr. Enric Coll Gelabert	Barcelona, Spain	Environmental Technician at Environmental Education and Promotion Office of the Barcelona Provincial Council	-
Mr. Epameinondas Christofilopoulos	Thessaloniki, Greece	Horizon 2020 National Expert for Climate Change	https://goo.gl/clZ1Yc
Dr. Eva Lievens	Leuven, Belgium	Professor of Law and Technology at the Law Faculty of Ghent University	https://goo.gl/khlOMZ
Mr. Joakim Jardnberg	Helsingborg, Sweden	Internet and Social Media Expert at Helsingborg	https://goo.gl/OuKGAQ
Ms. Eva Theisz	Stockholm, Sweden	Deputy Director of International Affairs at the Swedish public employment service	https://goo.gl/2LXkL3
Ms. Christiane Klemm	Greifswald, Germany	Board Member of Youth and Environment Europe	http://goo.gl/hUibce
Mr. Babis Tsitlakidis	Brussels, Belgium	DG CONNECT, Unit of eHealth and ICT for Wellbeing and Ageing	https://goo.gl/ogFR6y
Lorenzo Floresta	Caserta, Italy	Coordinator of the CATCH-EyoU project	-

ANNEX B – STEP EEAB update (November 2016)

step
Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

**Advisory Board Update
November 2016**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Where we are now and next steps

Until now

The 1st version of the **STEP platform** has been integrated. We are now at the phase of fine-tuning while we are planning to release the platform to the public in **February 2017**. The **STEP social media monitoring tool** has also been developed. As the platform is almost ready for the pilot testing, a **very detailed pilot plan** for each of our 5 pilot operational environments has been prepared identifying specific pilot procedures and defining an evaluation methodology for assessing their impact. We are happy to have also on board **an additional pilot member**, [Resilient Thessaloniki](#), who will voluntarily pilot use the STEP platform in Thessaloniki, Greece! Within this period, we have prepared the 2nd version of the **Data Management Plan** which describes how the data produced within the project will be curated and preserved. A 1st issue of the project **business plan** identifying the paths to market and a proposed business model has been prepared. Finally, regarding the project's dissemination, the final version of the STEP **dissemination plan** has been set, while the **dissemination activities** performed within the 1st year of the project operation have been reported.

Next steps

Our plan for the next months is to finalize the 1st version of the STEP platform and **train the pilot partners** on the use of the platform's components. **Pilot workshops and launch events** will be organized in each pilot area in order to maximize users' participation in the pilots. The **pilot operations** are expected to start in February 2017, while the **intermediate evaluation** of their progress will be performed in May 2017. All these months, **specific dissemination activities** will be performed all around Europe and especially in the pilot areas, while **dissemination material** addressing the needs of our target groups will be prepared and distributed.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Further insight

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

The platform

The 1st Version of the STEP platform is almost ready!

The core components, e.g. the e-participation platform, the social media mining & visualization tools, the machine translation & text-to-speech component, and the data logging component, **have been integrated**.

Unit testing, integration testing, user interface testing and security testing are being performed to ensure that the STEP platform meets its requirements and expected features properly.

After monitoring the pilot execution and receiving pilot's feedback, required developments and changes will be implemented for the **final version of the platform**.

For more information please visit the following link: [D3.2: Integrated and tested STEP platform](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

The social media monitoring tool

The initial version of the STEP **social media monitoring tool** has been developed. It facilitates the **identification** of the exact social media networks that young people prefer and it provides useful insights on **what content people engage with**. With this tool public authorities are able to **monitor the impact of an environmental campaign** they initiate, while young people can find out **what their peers talk about!** Further adaptations to this tool will be performed throughout the pilot operation according to the user feedback. Its final version will be available in **October 2017**.

The web tool for the STEP social media mining is released [here](#).

For more information please visit the following link:

[D4.3: Social media monitoring tool.](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Pilot plan

A detailed **pilot plan** and an **evaluation methodology** for assessing its impact have been prepared. The pilot will be implemented from November 2016 till November 2017 and it is broken down into 4 phases: *training, testing with core group of users, open pilot, and evaluation.*

Six local pilot plans have been set up in close collaboration with our pilot partners:

- ◊ Region of **Crete**, Greece
- ◊ **Hatay** Municipality, Turkey
- ◊ **Locride** area, Italy
- ◊ **Mollet de Valles** Municipality, Spain,
- ◊ **Valdemoro** Municipality, Spain
- ◊ Municipality of **Thessaloniki**, Greece (additional pilot not foreseen in the DoA!)

In the following pages you can find some interesting aspects of our pilot plans, while for more information please visit the following link: [D5.1: Definition of STEP pilots and evaluation methodology.](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Issues to be brought under public participation through STEP

1) Region of Crete

- ◉ **Environmental Impact Assessment procedures**
- ◉ **Energy** conservation issues
- ◉ **Water management** actions
- ◉ Protection of **NATURA** habits & protected species
- ◉ **Coastal zone** degradation
- ◉ **Wastewater** reclamation & reuse
- ◉ **Climate change**
- ◉ **Sustainable tourism**, ecotourism

2) Hatay Municipality

- ◉ Building a “**Green Eco-City**” together with the young citizens
- ◉ Round table with **policy-makers**
- ◉ Round table with **environmental experts & NGOs**
- ◉ Establishment of city **youth environmental assembly**
- ◉ Establishment of a masterplan for an **aromatic & medicinal plant park**
- ◉ **Urban gardening**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Issues to be brought under public participation through STEP

3) Locride area

- ◉ Proposal for **waste collection** door to door against the current road containers waste collection
- ◉ New ideas to introduce **waste sorting** at work, in schools, in public spaces
- ◉ Select locations for new **park areas** in the cities
- ◉ Proposal for **green water treatment plant**

4) Mollet de Valles Municipality

- ◉ Youth participation in the **city plan**
- ◉ Round table with **policy-makers**
- ◉ **Recycling**
- ◉ Creation of city **environmental volunteers**
- ◉ **Nature itineraries**
- ◉ **Mobility plan**
- ◉ STEP as a toll for **education**
- ◉ **Urban gardening**
- ◉ Local **food policies**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Issues to be brought under public participation through STEP

5) Valdemoro Municipality

- **Water savings**
- Proposals of **new park areas**
- **Urban Development Plan**
- Parks **reforestation**
- Reorganization of the urban **transport network**
- Locations of **garbage bins**
- **Litter** picking campaigns
- Design of the city's **bike lane**

6) Thessaloniki Municipality

- Evaluation on the **quality of urban environment** in Ntepo neighbourhood
- Consultation on the possibility to use the **school yards beyond the school operation** timeframe in order to provide open spaces to local community
- Mapping of places with significant **cultural interest**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Issues to be brought under public participation through STEP

5) Valdemoro Municipality

- **Water savings**
- Proposals of **new park areas**
- **Urban Development Plan**
- Parks **reforestation**
- Reorganization of the urban **transport network**
- Locations of **garbage bins**
- **Litter** picking campaigns
- Design of the city's **bike lane**

6) Thessaloniki Municipality

- Evaluation on the **quality of urban environment** in Ntepo neighbourhood
- Consultation on the possibility to use the **school yards beyond the school operation** timeframe in order to provide open spaces to local community
- Mapping of places with significant **cultural interest**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Data Management

The **European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation** released an updated version of the “Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020” on the 15th of February 2016. In the document it is clearly mentioned that a Data Management Plan should be regularly updated, thus an updated version of the STEP **Data Management Plan** has been prepared and released.

Specifically, all project partners provided the required information regarding the **inclusion of new data sets**, any changes in consortium policies or the existence of any external factors that would influence the status of the existing datasets.

For more information please visit the following link: [D1.4: 2nd Data Management Plan](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Business Plan

The first issue of the STEP Business Plan comprises the preliminary approach regarding the **paths to the market** and a **proposed business model** that may be adopted. We envision the following paths to the market:

- A set of **individual partners' exploitation plans**, which comprise the usage that will be given to the knowledge, products and services resulting from the STEP project.
- A **collaborative commercial initiative**, led by several partners of the consortium. This initiative is evaluating several legal figures such as joint ventures or associative approaches.

These paths will be **validated** through qualitative and/or quantitative market research tools with the most significant market players (e.g. potential customers, which comprise Public Authorities, software integrators and suppliers, etc.).

Market research and contacts with competitors have been approached in order to see how they are currently positioned, how they approach the market and the range of prices that is given to the current e-participation offering. The CANVAS methodology was used to structure the information needed. Business models of different products have been proposed, in order to validate with market players **the best cost-value added business model**.

The **final version of the STEP Business Plan** will be delivered in November 2017.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Dissemination

As regards the dissemination of the project, specialised **Local Dissemination Strategies** for the pilot areas have been also outlined.

You can have a look in the final version of the STEP dissemination plan here: [D7.7: 2nd Dissemination Plan](#)

The **dissemination tools** prepared and the **dissemination activities** performed during the 1st year of the project by all partners have been reported. Indicatively:

- the second issue of the project semi-annual [newsletter](#) has been released
- a STEP promotional [video](#) has been prepared
- an initial contact list of the members of the STEP [Network of Interest](#) has been established
- a STEP-relevant **scientific paper** was accepted & presented in the [Dual E-Government and E-Participation Conference 2016](#)
- all partners have presented STEP in various **targeted** events.

For more information please visit the following link: [D7.3:1st report on dissemination activities](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Next Advisory Board meeting

Individual meetings (either physical or virtual) will be organized with all the Advisory Board members

Date: To be discussed

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

<http://www.step4youth.eu/>

[STEP H2020 Project](#)

[STEP_H2020](#)

[STEP H2020 project](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

